
A Thorough Overview of the Article: Major Incidents That Shaped Aviation Security

Instructor: Asst. Prof. Hatice KÜÇÜKÖNAL

Author: Arif Gürdem Çetinkaya

Abstract

This review critically examines the article "Major Incidents That Shaped Aviation Security" by Michal Klenka, which explores the evolution of aviation security policies in response to significant historical incidents. The article highlights key events such as the Pan Am Flight 103 bombing, the 9/11 terrorist attacks, and other major hijackings that profoundly influenced global aviation practices. The study emphasizes the reactive nature of security measures and the need for a proactive approach to mitigate emerging threats. By analyzing advancements like passenger profiling, behavior pattern recognition, and international treaties, the article underscores the challenges of achieving global coordination in aviation security. This review evaluates the article's insights on the balance between technological innovation and operational feasibility in enhancing security measures. It concludes that while significant progress has been made, aviation security must continue to adapt preemptively to evolving threats, ensuring safe and resilient air transport systems globally.

Keywords: Aviation Security, Hijackings and Terrorism, Proactive Security Measures

JEL Classification: L93, K38

1. Introduction

Aviation security is vital for the safety of passengers and the smooth operation of international trade. Over the years, several major incidents have highlighted weaknesses in the system, leading to changes in security measures. Events like hijackings in the 1960s and the tragic 9/11 attacks have shaped how the aviation industry and governments address threats.

The article "Major Incidents That Shaped Aviation Security" by Michal Klenka explores how these events have influenced policies and technological advancements. It discusses the shift from basic methods like metal detectors to more advanced systems, such as biometric screening and behavior analysis. The article argues that aviation security has mostly been reactive, but a more proactive approach is needed to handle modern challenges.

This review focuses on the key points of the article, including the impact of historical events like the Pan Am Flight 103 bombing and newer threats like cyber-attacks. It also looks at the need for

international cooperation to create unified strategies. Balancing safety with efficient operations remains a challenge for aviation stakeholders.

By studying past incidents and their effects, the article offers insights into how the aviation industry can prepare for future risks and maintain its role as a reliable and safe mode of transportation.

2. Literature Review

The article "Major Incidents That Shaped Aviation Security" by Michal Klenka presents a detailed examination of aviation security policies shaped by historical incidents. It builds on a wide range of literature to discuss how hijackings, bombings, and other security breaches influenced the evolution of measures designed to safeguard civil aviation. The review explores several pivotal studies and reports that provide context and support for the article's arguments.

The article relies heavily on historical accounts to trace the trajectory of aviation security. Early incidents, such as the 1931 hijacking in Peru and the 1933 United Airlines bombing, are described as events that initially received little attention from authorities. The literature indicates that significant policy changes did not occur until the surge of hijackings in the 1960s and 1970s, such as those involving Cuba and the Middle East. These events prompted the introduction of the Anti-Hijacking Act of 1974, mandating passenger and baggage screening in the United States.

Later events, such as the Pan Am Flight 103 bombing over Lockerbie and the September 11, 2001, terrorist attacks, are highlighted as turning points in global aviation security. The article references studies discussing the implementation of technologies like metal detectors, x-ray scanners, and biometric systems. It also reviews the emergence of passenger profiling and behavior analysis as key strategies, particularly drawing on Israel's success with such methods.

Klenka addresses the reactive nature of aviation security, citing numerous studies to argue that many measures were implemented only after significant incidents. For example, the failure of the Sky Marshal Program and the eventual shift toward ground-based prevention are described using detailed literature references. The article also draws from works emphasizing the importance of international conventions, such as the Tokyo and Hague Conventions, while critiquing their limited effectiveness due to inconsistent global implementation.

Overall, the article synthesizes existing literature effectively, providing a comprehensive overview of the milestones in aviation security policy. However, it emphasizes the need for further research into proactive approaches and global coordination to combat emerging threats, such as cyber-attacks and unmanned aerial systems. This literature review establishes a strong foundation for the article's subsequent analysis and conclusions.

3. Important Issues

The article identifies several critical issues that have shaped aviation security over time. A recurring theme is the reactive nature of security measures, where new policies are introduced primarily in response to incidents rather than as proactive strategies. For example, the implementation of mandatory passenger screening in the 1970s only occurred after a surge in hijackings during the previous decade (Klenka, 2019).

Another significant issue discussed is the challenge of international coordination. While conventions like the Tokyo and Hague agreements laid the groundwork for global aviation security, their effectiveness has been hindered by inconsistent implementation and varying levels of commitment among countries. This lack of uniformity creates vulnerabilities in the global aviation network, particularly in regions with limited resources.

The article also emphasizes the balance between security and operational efficiency. Stringent measures, such as 100% baggage screening or the 300-ft rule for vehicles near terminals, are necessary but can disrupt airport operations and passenger convenience. Klenka (2019) notes that technological advancements, such as behavior pattern recognition, aim to enhance security without compromising efficiency.

Finally, the article highlights the emergence of modern threats like cyber-attacks, unmanned aerial systems, and liquid explosives. These threats demand innovative solutions, as traditional security methods may not suffice. For example, the downing of Metrojet Flight 9268 in 2015 underscored the limitations of existing measures against evolving tactics used by terrorists.

In summary, the article underscores the need for a proactive and integrated approach to aviation security. Addressing these important issues requires collaboration among stakeholders, continuous technological innovation, and a shift towards preventive strategies to mitigate future risks effectively.

4. Conclusion

The article "Major Incidents That Shaped Aviation Security" provides a clear overview of how major events have shaped aviation security policies over time. It highlights the reactive nature of many measures, showing that changes often came only after significant incidents like hijackings and terrorist attacks. Despite this, important advancements, such as passenger profiling, behavior analysis, and advanced screening technologies, have greatly improved air travel safety.

I believe the article effectively emphasizes the need for a proactive approach to aviation security. Modern threats like cyber-attacks and drone-related risks require more innovative and forward-thinking solutions than ever before. However, one area that could be improved is the level of global coordination.

The lack of consistent security practices between countries remains a major vulnerability, and I think stronger international partnerships are essential to address this gap.

In my opinion, the balance between maintaining security and ensuring operational efficiency is another critical challenge. While stricter measures may increase safety, they can also disrupt passenger experience and airport operations. Therefore, I feel it is important for aviation stakeholders to focus on finding solutions that integrate advanced technologies with seamless processes. Learning from past incidents is crucial, but the industry must also take bold steps to prepare for the future, ensuring both safety and efficiency in global air travel.

References

Klenka, M. (2019). Major incidents that shaped aviation security. *Journal of Transportation Security*, 12(1–2), 39–56. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12198-019-00201-2>